

Public Policy Design and National Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between public policy design and national development in Nigeria. The study focuses on understanding how policies are formulated, the factors that shape their design, and the challenges that hinder their impact. Using a qualitative approach, this study draws on policy documents, government reports, and existing literature to analyse the characteristics of public policy design and its alignment with Nigeria's developmental priorities. The study is anchored on the rational policy-making model to explore how political, economic, and institutional factors influence policy formulation. Findings revealed that while public policies are formulated with developmental objectives in mind, political considerations, bureaucratic limitations, and inadequate stakeholder engagement often constrain their effectiveness. The study recommended strengthening evidence-based policy design, enhancing participatory policy formulation by involving key stakeholders, and building institutional capacity to ensure that public policies effectively contribute to sustainable national development.

Keywords: Public Policy, Policy Design, National Development, Policy Formulation, Governance

Introduction

Public policy design is a critical component of national development because it sets the foundation for how government priorities, allocate resources, and coordinate its actions that influence socio-economic development within the state. In developing countries, especially in federal systems such as Nigeria, the process of public policy design encompasses identification problem, formulation of options, consultation with stakeholders, and selection of good strategies in line with national goals and citizen needs (Pillah, 2023). A good policy design should ideally integrate evidence-based analysis, inputs of stakeholder in order to produce public policies capable of addressing developmental challenges.

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In Nigeria, successive national development plans have struggled to translate strategic goals into tangible socio-economic progress serving as indication of weak public policy design and its application. Evidence suggest that, Nigeria's national development plans have been facing gaps in inclusivity, institutional capacity, and alignment with long-term development objectives, which undermine the ability of these policies to effectively respond to pressing national issues (Abasilim *et al* 2025). These design limitations are compounded by political dynamics, bureaucratic constraints, and variable use of evidence in decision-making processes, making it difficult to sustain policy coherence across sectors.

In Nigeria, researches have demonstrates systematic variation in the use of research evidence among federal policymakers, suggesting that the degree to which evidence influences policy content depends on individual capacities as well as institutional norms (Aremu *et al* 2026). Such dynamics influence not only what issues are prioritised but also how policies are structured to achieve development objectives. Therefore, a very good public policy design is key to the policy process and national development, as it directly affects policy content and anticipated impacts (Onimisi, 2025). Unfortunately, despite the importance of well-designed public policies, Nigeria's experience reveal some challenges in designing policy frameworks with developmental aspirations, raising questions about the underlying factors that shape policy design and how these can be improved. This study therefore, examines the relationship between public policy design and national development in Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Analyse how Public Policy design influences National Development in Nigeria.
2. Identify the political, economic, and institutional factors that shape Public Policy formulation in Nigeria.
3. Find out measures for improving Public Policy design to promote sustainable National Development in Nigeria.

Literature Review

It has been established that, public policy design is vital in shaping national development because it establishes the framework for prioritising societal problems, allocating resources, and implementing interventions (Pillah, 2023; Onimisi, 2025). In Nigeria, the design phase of public policy is particularly critical given the country's complex socio-economic challenges, weak institutions, and fragmented governance structures. Available literature suggests that effective policy design should integrate evidence, stakeholder engagement, institutional capacity, and political context to come up with policies that meaningfully address national development needs (Aremu *et al* 2026; Frontiers Sustainable Food Systems, 2024).

Over the years, national development plans in Nigeria have faced challenges in translating policy goals into tangible outcomes. Abasilim *et al* (2025) observed that weaknesses in inclusivity, institutional capacity, and coordination undermine the effectiveness of Nigeria's development plans. Shimawua (2025) revealed similar issues,

noting that poor integration of multi-sectoral inputs and limited stakeholder consultation have weakened the alignment of policy frameworks with national priorities. Okikiola (2025) argued further that systematic policy formulation processes, including structured consultation and adaptive feedback, remain underdeveloped, limiting the strategic potential of policy design.

Policy making that is evidence-based is widely recognised as critical for policy relevance and effectiveness. Aremu *et al* (2026) in his study identify variations in how Nigerian policymakers utilise evidence, showing that engagement with scientific research, data analytics, and expert reports is inconsistent across sectors. Uneke *et al* (2017) discovered similar gaps in health policy, where insufficient incorporation of research evidence reduced policy effectiveness. These studies indicate that limited use of evidence can hinder the design of policies capable of addressing

More so, Institutional and political factors significantly shape policy design. Onimisi (2025) notes that power dynamics, interest groups and political pressures do influence which issues enter the policy agenda and how they are framed. Yunana & Pantuvo (2023) in their study, highlight the impact of elite influence, corruption and frequent government changes on policy stability and coherence. In addition, weak institutional capacity and bureaucratic inefficiencies further limit the alignment of policy design with national development objectives (Asaju, 2025; Bulus *et al* 2025).

Nigeria's federal structure added to complexities in policy design. Ezeudu & kolie (2025) demonstrate that coordination issues between federal, state, and local governments blur responsibilities and reduce policy clarity.

Researches on Nigeria's historical development plans revealed weaknesses in policy formulation and execution. Bulus *et al* (2025) emphasise that past national development plans lacked integration with ground realities, undermining their developmental impact. Similarly, Abasilim *et al* (2025) and Shimawua (2025) document that past public policies were not consistently incorporate stakeholder input or adapt to changing socio-economic contexts, highlighting the enduring challenges in policy design.

Therefore, it is understood that public policy design is a dynamic process influenced by multiple actors and institutional arrangements (Pillah, 2023; Okikiola, 2025). Evidence from the review carried out suggests that policy design is not just technical formulation but involves negotiation, prioritisation, and integration of evidence within political and institutional realities (Frontiers Sustainable Food Systems, 2024). Effective design, therefore, requires both analytical rigor and sensitivity to governance dynamics to produce policies that can meaningfully impact national development outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Rational Choice Theory. This theory is one of the most widely recognised theories in public policy analysis. Central assumption of this theory is that policymakers act as rational actors who make decisions by weighing costs, benefits, and possible outcomes to maximise social or economic utility (Weimer & Vining, 2021).

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The theory laid more emphasises systematic, evidence-based, and goal-oriented decision-making, making it highly relevant for examining the design of public policies and their impact on national development.

Applying this theory in the Nigerian allows the study to assess how policy design decisions consider national development priorities, resource constraints, and socio-political realities. The theory also helps explain why some public policies succeed while others fail, especially when political pressures, institutional weaknesses, or poor evidence use interfere with rational decision-making (Aremu *et al* 2026; Pillah, 2023).

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research design using secondary data to examine the relationship between public policy design and national development in Nigeria. The qualitative approach is suitable because it enables an in-depth review of existing policy documents, national development plans, government reports, and peer-reviewed scholarly literature, providing insights into policy formulation processes, institutional frameworks, and governance dynamics (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). By relying exclusively on secondary data, the study captures historical and contemporary patterns in public policy design and its developmental implications without the need for primary data collection (Pillah, 2023; Aremu *et al* 2026). The gathered data were analysed using thematic content analysis to identify and interpret recurring themes and patterns within the documents

Discussion

Influence of Public Policy Design on National Development in Nigeria

Public policy design is a critical determinant of national development because it establishes the blueprint through which governmental priorities are operationalised into actionable programs and strategic interventions. In Nigeria, the quality of policy design has been shown to significantly affect economic growth, social welfare, and institutional effectiveness (Aremu *et al* 2026; Pillah, 2023). Public policies that are effectively designed always incorporate clear objectives, evidence-based strategies, stakeholder consultation, and mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation, which collectively enhance the potential for achieving development goals (Frontiers Sustainable Food Systems, 2024; Bulus *et al* 2025). On the contrast, Policies that are poorly designed or misaligned with institutional capacities, governance frameworks, or socio-economic realities often result in fragmented implementation, limited developmental impact, and public dissatisfaction (Abasilim *et al* 2025; Yunana & Pantuvo, 2023).

Studies indicated that, national development plans Nigerian while articulating sectoral priorities such as healthcare, education, infrastructure, and agriculture, frequently face challenges in translating these priorities into actionable policies (Shimawua, 2025; Okikiola, 2025). It has been established that, the success of policy design depends on the integration of coherent strategies, realistic implementation mechanisms, and alignment with institutional capabilities. Scholars assert that evidence-informed approaches to policy design, where empirical research informs decision-making, enhance the credibility

and effectiveness of development initiatives (Aremu, 2024; Pillah, 2023). Conversely, when these factors are neglected, policies do not translate to national development objectives.

It has also been found that, political and governance dynamics also influence the impact of policy design on development. Onimisi (2025) notes that elite interests, partisan considerations, and political patronage often shape policy priorities, resulting in designs that prioritise political expediency over sustainable development. The Rational Choice perspective suggests that policymakers who systematically consider trade-offs, resource constraints, and socio-political realities are more likely to design policies that achieve measurable developmental outcomes (Weimer & Vining, 2021). This approach highlights the need for a deliberate alignment of policy goals with institutional capacities and long-term national objectives.

In addition, the institutional environment including bureaucratic effectiveness, inter-agency coordination, and administrative capacity critically determines whether well-intended policy designs are implementable (Abasilim *et al* 2025). Studies emphasise that policies aligned with institutional capabilities and structured to facilitate coordination across ministries and levels of government are more likely to produce sustainable development outcomes (Bulus *et al* 2025; Pillah, 2023). Public policies that ignore these institutional realities suffer delays, inefficiencies, or partial execution, limiting their developmental impact.

Finally, evidently established that, a robust public policy design in fostering national development. Aligning policy objectives with socio-economic priorities, ensuring institutional readiness, integrating evidence-based approaches, and accommodating governance and political realities collectively enhance the effectiveness of policies in promoting economic growth, social equity and institutional resilience (Aremu *et al* 2026; Yunana & Pantuvo, 2023). Therefore, the design phase is a decisive factor in determining whether public policy initiatives can deliver measurable and sustainable development outcomes in Nigeria.

Factors Shaping Public Policy Formulation in Nigeria

The formulation of public policy in Nigeria is influenced by institutional structures, which define how decisions are made, how responsibilities are allocated, and how policies are implemented. Institutional capacity, including bureaucratic expertise, coordination among government agencies, and procedural efficiency, shapes the analytical quality of policy design (Pillah, 2023). When institutional frameworks are weak, there is limited technical capacity, and inadequate mechanisms for inter-agency collaboration policy formulation will faced constraints. More, scholars emphasise that policies developed without considering institutional realities tend to be technically ambitious but practically unfeasible, leading to implementation challenges and limited developmental impact (Aremu *et al* 2026; Abasilim *et al* 2025).

More so, political dynamics are a key determinant of policy formulation in Nigeria. Onimisi (2025) notes that, the influence of political elites, party interests, and

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executive priorities often shapes which issues are emphasised in national policy agendas. Policy design in Nigeria is frequently affected by political considerations, such as populist demands, election cycles, and power bargaining among elite actors, which can result in the prioritisation of short-term objectives over long-term national development. Yunana & Pantuvo (2023) while contributing on this, observe that, political patronage, elite dominance, and bureaucratic politicisation often distort policy priorities, leading to policies that reflect the interests of a few rather than the broader public good. These political pressures can compromise policy coherence, reduce stability across government administrations, and affect the alignment of policies with development goals.

Another important factor is economic factors and resource constraints which significantly shape public policy formulation in Nigeria. Fiscal limitations, fluctuations in oil revenue, and competing demands for scarce resources influence policy priorities and the selection of policy instruments. According to Aremu (2024), economic pressures often restrict the scope of evidence considered during policy formulation and limit the feasibility of ambitious developmental programs. Public policies formulated under tight economic constraints tend to prioritise immediate stabilisation measures over long-term development interventions, which can limit their effectiveness in addressing structural socio-economic challenges such as poverty, unemployment, and infrastructure deficits.

Lastly, the federal structure of Nigeria adds another layer of complexity to public policy formulation. Coordination among federal, state, and local governments is crucial for ensuring that national policies are aligned with local realities and developmental needs. Abasilim *et al* (2025) emphasise that policy misalignment across governance levels frequently undermines the effectiveness of national development plans. Effective policy formulation requires engagement with multiple stakeholders across

Measures for Improving Public Policy Design to Promote Sustainable National Development in Nigeria

Scholarly researches have proffered measures to be taken to improve public policy design. As discussed earlier, public policy design is a critical determinant of the sustainability of national development initiatives, as it establishes the frameworks, strategies, and mechanisms through which programs are executed and monitored. It has been observed that policies designed with clear objectives, well-defined strategies, and practical implementation mechanisms are more likely to achieve long-term developmental outcomes (Aremu *et al* 2026; Pillah, 2023). In Nigeria, public policies that fail to consider sustainability principles often lead to fragmented implementation, limited continuity across administrations, and minimal long-term impact on socio-economic development. Research shows that sustainability in policy design requires integrating financial feasibility, institutional readiness, and governance considerations to ensure that initiatives are resilient to political and economic shocks (Bulus *et al* 2025; Abasilim *et al* 2025).

More so, the durability of development initiatives also depends on the inclusion of monitoring and evaluation mechanisms during the policy design phase. Scholars

highlight that feedback loops, performance indicators, and systematic assessment frameworks enable policymakers to track progress, identify challenges, and adjust policies accordingly (Pillah, 2023; Aremu, 2024). In Nigeria, the absence of robust monitoring systems has been cited as a major factor contributing to the premature termination of programs and the inability to achieve intended development objectives. Policies that incorporate adaptive management approaches are more resilient and responsive, allowing national development initiatives to sustain their objectives despite changing political or socio-economic conditions (Yunana & Pantuvo, 2023).

In addition, political stability and continuity of governance play a significant role in the sustainability of development-focused policies. Onimisi (2025) notes that frequent changes in government leadership, coupled with policy reversals, undermine the capacity of national development initiatives to produce long-term results. Policies designed without mechanisms to ensure continuity, institutional memory, or cross-administration support often face disruptions, limiting their effectiveness. Scholars suggest that sustainable policy design must include strategies that transcend electoral cycles and promote intergovernmental coordination to maintain the trajectory of national development programs (Shimawua, 2025; Okikiola, 2025).

Economic viability is another critical factor in sustaining national development initiatives. Nigeria's dependence on volatile revenue sources, particularly oil, affects the implementation and continuation of policy-driven programs (Aremu, 2024; Bulus *et al* 2025). Well-designed policies incorporate realistic budgeting, resource allocation frameworks, and prioritisation strategies that align with available economic resources. Policies that fail to account for fiscal constraints or lack financial sustainability mechanisms are at risk of being truncated, compromising developmental goals and reducing public trust in governance structures.

Finally, scholars emphasise that holistic and integrated policy design enhances both the sustainability and effectiveness of national development initiatives. Evidence suggests that policies aligned with institutional capacity, political realities, economic conditions, and societal needs are more likely to be implemented successfully and deliver measurable outcomes (Aremu, *et al* 2026; Pillah, 2023; Yunana & Pantuvo, 2023).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that public policy design is central to the advancement of national development in Nigeria. Effective policy design provides a structured approach for translating government priorities into tangible programs, but its success is contingent upon strong institutional capacity, coherent governance structures, and consideration of political and economic realities. Policies that are poorly designed or misaligned with institutional and societal needs often face implementation challenges, limited sustainability, and reduced developmental impact. Conversely, policies that incorporate evidence-based strategies, inclusive stakeholder engagement, and adaptive mechanisms are more likely to achieve long-term goals, remain resilient across political and economic shifts, and contribute meaningfully to national development. The findings underscore the necessity of a holistic and integrated approach to policy formulation, ensuring that public

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policies are both effective and sustainable in addressing Nigeria's developmental challenges.

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